

CHALLENGES OF MULTI-GRADE TEACHERS IN ESL: BASIS FOR THE PROPOSED ENHANCED CAPACITY FOR MULTIGRADE ESL TEACHING

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Challenges of Multi-grade Teachers in ESL: Basis for the Proposed Enhanced Capacity for Multigrade ESL Teaching

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Abstract

This study assessed the specific issues encountered by teachers of various grades, including crucial areas like training, timetable, instructional materials, classroom management, and language barriers. This study used a convergent parallel mixed-methods research design, wherein qualitative and quantitative techniques were combined to examine the challenges of 101 multigrade teachers across the 12 districts in Siargao Division, Philippines, using survey questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions. Purposive sampling was used, whereas frequency count, percentage distribution, mean, standard deviation, ANOVA, Scheffé's test were applied to analyze the data. This study is anchored in Vygotsky's Social Constructivism and Biddle's Teacher Role Theory, the results showed that although challenges in training, instructional materials, and classroom management are not as prominent serious challenges remain in time management and language barriers. Younger, novice, and non-married teachers, and those in lower teaching positions or with less educational attainment, faced heightened challenging training, timetabling, and classroom management. Teachers of Grades 1 and 2 faced more problems regarding the timetable compared to teachers teaching higher grades, and teachers with lower performance ratings faced more problems in all five aspects. These findings underscore the necessity to have targeted interventions to address these persistent barriers. Thus, the program "Enhanced Capacity for Multigrade ESL Teaching" would take shape to empower the multigrade teacher for the betterment of the learning outcomes.

Keywords: *multigrade teaching, ESL instruction, teacher challenges, time management, language barriers*

Introduction

Multigrade schools are usually found in mountainous or dispersed island locations and play a significant role in delivering education to places where it is impractical for traditional single-grade classes owing to low enrollment and scarce resources. Multigrade schools are a hope for learning in the Philippines's varied and difficult terrain. They truly are lifesavers in the case of the isolated and thinly inhabited communities in the Siargao Division, part of the Caraga region.

The government started the Multigrade Program in Philippine Education by making primary education as free and accessible as possible to all Filipino children. This program was formally established by DepEd Order No. 86. The system aimed at closing the educational gap in isolated barangays by creating multigrade schools in areas where regular single-grade classes were impossible. Still, despite very admirable goals for the system, there have been some serious difficulties that have been severely testing teachers' adaptation and resiliency all throughout the country. There are tremendous stakes in multigrade settings because the teacher has to address a broad range of ages and abilities across grade levels, with a curriculum that is meant to be concurrent across several grade levels. Inadequate training, ill-planned schedules, and the difficult task of controlling classroom dynamics with few teaching resources are but a few of the many difficulties that these teachers face, as recent studies have shown.

According to Olivo (2021), the concurrent pressure of managing multiple learning needs and maintaining discipline is overrunning teachers in multigrade classes in the Philippines. They underscored that teachers need more classroom management training suited to multigrade settings so they can better use their time in a more organized way. In addition, Rotas (2021) emphasized that professional satisfaction among multigrade teachers indicates the demands of managing multiple grade levels with limited resources can lead to significant stress and burnout. This underlined the importance of adequate training and support for teachers in such settings. The problems potentially threatening the education futures of the children relying on such multigrade systems are not just threats to effective instruction.

Considering these challenges, it is crucial to understand the particular issues multigrade teachers encounter in teaching ESL is crucial. Thus, this study assessed the Challenges of Multi-grade Teachers in ESL that focused on five broad themes: training, timetable, instructional materials, classroom management, and language barrier as the Basis for the Proposed Enhanced Capacity for Multigrade ESL Teaching. This focused on improving standard instruction in multigrade settings and making sure even the most isolated communities in the Philippines receive the education they need and are entitled to.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges of Multi-grade Teachers in ESL: Basis for the proposed Enhanced Capacity for Multigrade ESL Teaching (ECMET) program in the 12 Districts of Siargao Division, Dapa, Surigao del Norte during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to:

- 1.1. age;
- 1.2. gender;
- 1.3. civil status;
- 1.4. teaching position;
- 1.5. grade level handled;
- 1.6. length of teaching experience of multigrade;
- 1.7. highest educational attainment;
- 1.8. performance rating;
- 1.9. mean percentage scores?
2. What are the challenges met by the multigrade teachers in ESL in terms of:
 - 2.1. training;
 - 2.2. timetable;
 - 2.3. instructional materials;
 - 2.4. classroom management;
 - 2.5. language barrier?
3. Is there a significant difference in the challenges met by the multigrade teachers when grouped according to their profile?
4. Based on the findings, what intervention plan may be proposed?

Methodology

This study used a convergent parallel mixed-methods research design, wherein qualitative and quantitative techniques were combined to examine the challenges of 101 multigrade teachers across the 12 districts in Siargao Division, Philippines, while teaching English as a second language. The quantitative phase employed a descriptive-correlational research design to obtain quantifiable data on five key challenges: training, timetable, instructional materials, classroom management, and language barriers. A self-developed and pilot-tested survey questionnaire was used, consisting of two parts: demographic information and closed-ended questions with Likert scale ratings. To analyze the quantitative data, frequency count, percentage distribution, mean, standard deviation, ANOVA, Scheffé's test were applied.

For participant selection, the convenient purposive sampling technique was used to determine the 101 multigrade teacher respondents, as this was the most appropriate method to include all multigrade teachers in Siargao Division.

Meanwhile, the qualitative phase of the study employed a phenomenological research design, aiming to gain in-depth insights into the lived experiences of multigrade teachers regarding the identified challenges. 10 participants were selected through a screener survey and chosen using criterion-based purposive sampling, as they were multigrade teachers with multitasking roles across the 12 districts of Siargao Division. In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) were conducted using a semi-structured discussion guide designed to elicit detailed narratives about their experiences and coping mechanisms.

To analyze the qualitative data, thematic analysis was used. The recorded FGDs were transcribed, coded, and categorized into emerging themes following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework. This approach ensured that recurring patterns and significant insights were systematically identified and interpreted.

Results and Discussion

Based on the result of the survey questionnaire about the profile of the respondents, the following data is collected and presented.

Table 1. *Displays the distribution of Respondents from the 12 districts of Siargao Division*

<i>Multigrade School Per Districts</i>	<i>No. Of Respondents</i>
Burgos District	5
Dapa East District	1
Dapa West District	7
General Luna District	17
Numancia East District	4
Numancia West District	11
Pilar District	10
San Benito District	9
San Isidro District	16
Sapao District	4
Socorro East District	1
Socorro West District	16
Total	101

Based on the table above, there are 101 total respondents from the Multigrade Schools in the 12 districts of the Siargao Division.

Table 2. Profile of Respondents

	Profile	f(n=101)	Percent
Age	21-29	34	33.7
	30-39	48	47.5
	40 and above	19	18.8
Gender	Male	10	9.9
	Female	91	90.1
Civil Status	Married	65	64.4
	Single/Separated/Annulled/Widowed	36	35.6
Position	Teacher I	71	70.3
	Teacher II	9	8.9
	Teacher III and higher	21	20.8
Grade Level Handled	Grade 1 & 2	19	18.8
	Grades 3 & 4	36	35.6
	Grade 5 & 6	32	31.7
	Kindergarten and Other Grade Level	14	13.9
Length of Teaching Experience	1-5 years	58	57.4
	6-10 years	27	26.7
	11-15 years	9	8.9
	16-20 years	7	6.9
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	35	34.7
	Master's Units	61	60.4
	At Least master's degree	5	5.0
Performance	Satisfactory	14	13.9
	Very Satisfactory	82	81.2
	Outstanding	5	5.0
Mean Percentage Score Description	Nearly Mastered	94	93.1
	Mastered	7	6.9

Presented in Table 2 are the profiles of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, civil status, position, grade level handled, highest educational attainment, performance, and mean percentage scores description. Based on the table above, respondents were mostly married females who were 30-39 years old, mostly Teacher I handled Grades 3 and 4, with 1 to 5 years of teaching experience with Master's unit and having very satisfactory performance.

Challenges Met by ESL Multigrade Teachers

Table 3 outlines the training challenges faced by ESL multigrade teachers.

Table 3. Training Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers

Statement	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I never experienced even one training on how to teach multigrade learners.	2.23	1.22	Disagree	Less Evident
2. The training/s was/were made in a hurry, so I never learned a lot.	2.01	1.06	Disagree	Less Evident
3. The training/s was/were less focused on the teaching strategies in handling multigrade classes.	2.12	1.01	Disagree	Less Evident
4. The training/s never taught how to solve problems that may occur in teaching multigrade pupils.	2.00	0.97	Disagree	Less Evident
5. The training/s never provided me the skills on how to develop or make relevant instructional materials for the diversified learners in multigrade class.	1.98	0.99	Disagree	Less Evident
Average	2.07	0.94	Disagree	Less Evident

Legend: 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree | 1.50 - 2.49 = Disagree | 2.50 - 3.49 = Agree | 3.50 - 4.00 = Strongly Agree
 1.00 - 1.49 = Not Evident | 1.50 - 2.49 = Less Evident | 2.50 - 3.49 = Moderately Evident | 3.50 - 4.00 = Highly Evident

Based on the table above, the respondents generally disagreed with the statements about the training for multigrade teaching. They found that training sessions were less evident in addressing specific challenges of multigrade teaching, such as teaching strategies, problem-solving, and instructional material development for diverse learners. However, the overall mean score of 2.07, with a standard deviation of 0.94, indicates that while these concerns are acknowledged, they are not strongly evident among the respondents.

In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion

Q1. Please describe your challenges in attending trainings relevant to Multigrade teaching. Truly relevant? Did you learn?

In interviews with multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte, several key themes emerged regarding the challenges and learning experiences related to attending trainings on multigrade teaching.

Relevance of Training Content. Many teachers felt that the content of the training sessions did not directly align with the specific needs of multigrade classrooms. The training often covered general or monograde teaching strategies that required modification to be applicable in their unique setting. For example, Participant 1 noted:

“The content of the training, while helpful, isn’t always applicable to a multigrade setting. Sometimes, it’s too focused on a monograde set-up, so we struggle to adjust the strategies they’re teaching.”

Challenges with Travel and Logistics. Teachers faced significant logistical challenges, such as long travel distances to attend training sessions, often requiring them to leave their classrooms and families behind. This led to concerns about missed instructional time for students. Participant 6 shared:

“Traveling long distances, dealing with the exhaustion, and then trying to absorb everything can be overwhelming. But I always try to see the positive side.”

Financial Constraints. Limited budgets for training often meant that teachers had to cover expenses like transportation, food, and accommodation from their own pockets, which was challenging due to their modest salaries. This financial burden discouraged some teachers from fully participating in the training they wished to attend. Participant 2 expressed:

“The budget for these trainings is limited. Not all expenses are covered, like transportation, food, and accommodation. That’s why sometimes we hesitate because our salary is also small.”

Time Management and Scheduling Issues. Scheduling conflicts between training sessions and teachers’ classroom hours created difficulties, as teachers had to balance attending training with their responsibility to be present for their students. This often resulted in missed lessons, which added to their workload when they returned. Participant 2 also highlighted this challenge:

“The schedule often doesn’t fit with our class hours. The trainings are usually held in far places, away from Siargao, so we have to travel and take leave, which means there are days we’re not in the classroom. Sometimes, the students miss lessons because we’re not there.”

Adaptation and Positive Takeaways. Despite these challenges, many teachers expressed a positive mindset, highlighting their efforts to adapt the content to their classrooms. They viewed training as an opportunity to gain new perspectives, even if the material wasn’t always directly relevant.

Participant 8 mentioned: “I approach these sessions with an open mind. I always find useful lessons even when the training isn’t quite in line with my multigrade setup”.

Q2. How did you handle these challenges?

The responses from the multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte highlight a variety of strategies they use to cope with the challenges of attending training relevant to multigrade teaching.

Adaptation and Resourcefulness. Teachers adjust and adapt the content from training to meet the specific needs of their multigrade classrooms, often by simplifying, modifying, or combining activities to fit their students’ levels.

"I started tweaking the ideas from the training to fit my classroom. I’d combine activities or break them down to make sure they worked for both grades." (Participant 6).

"I try to make the most of what I do learn. I take the ideas that are somewhat relevant and adapt them to fit my classroom." (Participant 1)

Collaboration and Peer Support. Teachers frequently collaborate with their peers, sharing insights, strategies, and resources to enhance their learning and improve classroom practices.

"I connected with other multigrade teachers and shared insights. We often discuss how to adapt the training content to our needs and support each other." (Participant 3)

"I shared these adjusted strategies with other teachers in the same situation. We’ve built a little network of support." (Participant 7)

Proactive Preparation and Adaptation. Teachers prepare ahead for training by considering logistical factors such as time and expenses and actively seek ways to make the training more relevant to their context.

"If there is training posted ahead of time, I will prepare myself regarding the expenses and the time as well." (Participant 2)

"When I get back from the training, I sit down with my co-teachers, and we share what we learned. It’s like piecing together a puzzle." (Participant 8)

Leveraging Experience and Continuous Learning. Teachers rely on their years of experience to adapt training content to the needs of their classrooms. They also emphasize the importance of continuous professional development and the pursuit of new resources.

"I leverage my years of experience and collaborate with fellow teachers to share and refine strategies." (Participant 10)

"I become very resourceful over the years. If I am not attending a training, I ask my colleagues to share what they have learned."

Creativity and Innovation in Problem-Solving. Teachers embrace the challenges of multigrade teaching, using creativity and innovative problem-solving to implement strategies that work for their specific classroom environment.

"I get to appreciate the challenge because it becomes the one that is pushing me to be more creative and resourceful. I feel like I am always growing and that is a good thing even when it hurts." (Participant 9)

"I started tweaking the ideas from the training to fit my classroom. And I didn't stop there—I shared these adjusted strategies with other teachers in the same situation." (Participant 6)

Timetable Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers

The table outlines the timetable challenges met by ESL multigrade teachers.

Table 4. *Timetable Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers*

Statement	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. The lack of time in multigrade classes makes me struggle to do my task.	2.92	0.77	Agree	Moderately Evident
2. I have a risk of time to properly cover the lessons of my multigrade classes.	2.86	0.80	Agree	Moderately Evident
3. I have difficulty finding creative solutions to address time constraints in a multigrade classroom.	2.70	0.71	Agree	Moderately Evident
4. Less time in a multigrade class pushes me more pressure and stress.	2.81	0.73	Agree	Moderately Evident
5. I have ineffective ability to address individual student needs because of limited time.	2.56	0.81	Agree	Moderately Evident
Average	2.77	0.64	Agree	Moderately Evident

Legend: 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree / 1.50 - 2.49 = Disagree / 2.50 - 3.49 = Agree / 3.50 - 4.00 = Strongly Agree
1.00 - 1.49 = Not Evident / 1.50 - 2.49 = Less Evident / 2.50 - 3.49 = Moderately Evident / 3.50 - 4.00 = Highly Evident

The results indicate that multigrade teachers generally agree that time constraints in multigrade classrooms pose significant challenges, with an overall average of 2.77 (moderately evident). Respondents struggle with completing tasks, covering lessons, and addressing individual student needs effectively due to limited time. These constraints also contribute to stress and pressure, with some difficulty in finding creative solutions to manage these challenges. While the issues are not highly evident, they remain a moderate and consistent concern among teachers.

In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion

Q1. Did you have time constraints in handling Multigrade classes? Please describe.

The responses from the multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte provide valuable insight into the challenges they face in managing time constraints while handling multigrade classes. The following themes emerge from their experiences: Time Allocation Challenges, Juggling Multiple Grade Levels, Balancing Quality and Quantity of Instruction, and Organizational Strategies for Time Management. These themes underscore the complexities of balancing diverse learning needs within a limited timeframe.

Time Allocation Challenges. Teachers face difficulties in distributing time effectively across multiple grades, often feeling rushed and stretched thin as they try to meet the demands of each group.

"Yes, time is an issue. Multigrade is pretty challenging because I find it difficult to allocate time to grade levels. Sometimes I get stretched too thin to give each grade level the attention that needs to occur in that time frame." (Participant 2)

"Yes, time constraints are the big challenge. With students across multiple grades, it's difficult to give each group proper time. You always feel that you rushed through covering everything." (Participant 3)

Juggling Multiple Grade Levels. Teachers describe the overwhelming task of handling two or more grade levels at the same time, comparing it to juggling multiple responsibilities and tasks in a short period.

"Oh, absolutely! In a multi-grade class, at the same time, it's like trying to juggle several balls in the air, and there's always the feeling that something is dropped, so there's a rush to ensure every group gets the required amount of time." (Participant 6)

"Time is really running out, Ma'am. Think about overseeing two grade levels at the same time. For example, with so many topics to be done, and the other group also needing attention, it is a bit challenging to concentrate on only one." (Participant 1).

Balancing Quality and Quantity of Instruction. Teachers struggle to balance the need to cover all required materials with the desire to provide each student with the attention and instruction they deserve.

"Well, managing time in multigrade classes is quite tricky". Since there are requirements and learning competencies for every grade level that need to be accommodated in the set time, teaching third and fourth graders is just a balancing act continually. Sometimes it gets overwhelming." (Participant 9)

"Yes, time constraints are definitely a challenge in multigrade classes, especially when you're managing both Grade 1 and 2. There's only so much time in a day, and trying to cover the curriculum for two different grades simultaneously can be overwhelming." (Participant 8)

Organizational Strategies for Time Management. Despite time constraints, teachers use organizational strategies to stay focused and manage the challenges of multitasking in multigrade classrooms.

"Sometimes, I feel like I'm just rushing through everything to make sure I don't leave out any topics." (Participant 4)

"It really pushes you to stay organized and focused." (Participant 6)

Q2. How did you manage to meet your lesson objectives despite time constraints?

The themes that emerge from their responses include **Prioritizing Key Objectives**, **Integrating Lessons for Efficiency**, **Utilizing Group Work and Peer Learning**, **Breaking Down Lessons into Manageable Segments**, and **Strategic Planning and Flexibility**.

Prioritizing Key Objectives. Teachers focus on the most essential learning goals, ensuring that critical content is covered while adjusting or omitting less urgent material to stay on track.

"By focusing on core objectives and by sometimes combining lessons for different grades, I fill the core material. It's a bit of a compromise, but it helps." (participant 1)

"I maintain my focus on critical learning objectives and lesson planning to achieve the right level of simplicity with my lectures. I also tailor my methods according to the requirements of the students." (Participant 4)

Integrating Lessons for Efficiency. Teachers creatively combine lessons for different grades, allowing them to teach similar concepts at varying levels of complexity and reduce redundancy.

"Through the years, I have evolved a few strategies that really pay off. One of the things I do most effectively is to connect lessons when possible." (Participant 9)

"I focus on prioritizing what's most important objectives, and I try to integrate lessons so that different levels can learn together, even if they're working on different tasks." (Participant 6)

Utilizing Group Work and Peer Learning. Group activities and peer teaching are used to maximize student engagement and allow teachers to work more efficiently, especially when managing multiple grades at once.

"I do group activities. I try to keep all students active and utilize each minute. It's all about flexibility, and creativity in any lesson that I do." (Participant 5)

"I encourage my students to help each other—peer teaching can be such a beautiful thing. It not only saves time but also builds a sense of community and support among them." (Participant 6)

Breaking Down Lessons into Manageable Segments. Teachers simplify and break down lessons into smaller, more digestible parts, allowing them to focus on essential components without overwhelming students.

"I breakdown the lessons into smaller chunks. I do group activities to keep all people participating and actually using every minute of time." (Participant 5)

"To accomplish my lesson intentions within the time available, I plan and organize carefully to be efficient. I divide the lesson into smaller portions that all grade levels can engage in activities that will help them best." (Participant 10)

Strategic planning and flexibility. Teachers express the necessity of strategic planning prior to teaching and flexibility during the teaching process that would adapt accordingly if time were insufficient to perform all the objectives.

"I had to strategize, Ma'am. I created lesson plans that integrated topics for both grade levels as much as possible." (Participant 4)

"It's all about being flexible and creative—sometimes I'll have one grade work independently while I give direct instruction to the other, and then switch." (Participant 9)

Instructional Material Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers

The table outlines the Instructional Material challenges met by ESL multigrade teachers.

The results show that teachers moderately agree with the challenges related to instructional materials in multigrade classrooms, with an overall average of 2.49 (less evident). Key concerns include having limited materials, difficulty catering to diverse learning needs, and materials being suitable only for specific activities or assessments. However, they disagree with statements about the reusability of materials and their attractiveness to students, suggesting these issues are less significant. Overall, while challenges exist, they are not strongly evident.

Table 5. *Instructional Material Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>QD</i>
1. I only have a few instructional materials that I use in my multigrade class.	2.61	0.81	Agree	Moderately Evident
2. My instructional materials are so hard to cater the different learning needs of my students.	2.53	0.79	Agree	Moderately Evident
3. My instructional materials are just applicable to some assessments or activities.	2.57	0.74	Agree	Moderately Evident
4. The available instructional materials are so tough to reuse for the next school year.	2.44	0.70	Disagree	Less Evident
5. My instructional materials are less attractive to the eyes of my students especially that they are interested in gadgets.	2.29	0.75	Disagree	Less Evident
Average	2.49	0.65	Disagree	Less Evident

*Legend: 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree / 1.50 - 2.49 = Disagree / 2.50 - 3.49 = Agree / 3.50 - 4.00 = Strongly Agree
1.00 - 1.49 = Not Evident / 1.50 - 2.49 = Less Evident / 2.50 - 3.49 = Moderately Evident / 3.50 - 4.00 = Highly Evident*

In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion

Q1. Please describe problems in handling multigrade classes in terms of instructional materials.

Responses from Siargao Division multigrade teachers, in Surigao del Norte, indicate the difficulties these classroom teachers face in managing instructional materials. The same themes of inappropriate material; need to adapt or create; and difficulty balancing the needs of different grade levels at the same time are mentioned. These themes tell of the resourcefulness of the teachers in making ends meet and adapting themselves in these situations to be effective.

Lack of Appropriate Materials. Teachers frequently encounter a shortage of instructional materials that are suitable for multigrade classrooms, where students of different ages and academic levels are present. Many existing materials are designed for single-grade classrooms, making them inadequate for multigrade settings.

"The main issue is the lack of suitable materials for different grade levels. Many resources are designed for single-grade classes, so I often need to create or adapt materials to fit all the different needs." (Participant 1)

"One of the big problems is the lack of appropriate materials for each grade level. We often don't have enough resources, so I end up creating a lot of my own." (Participant 7)

Adapting and Creating Materials. Given the shortage of suitable resources, teachers often have to modify existing materials or create new ones to meet the needs of their students. This requires extra time and effort but is necessary to ensure that students have the appropriate tools to learn.

"The main problem is finding materials that suit all the different grade levels. Many resources are not designed for multigrade settings, so I end up modifying or creating my own materials to fit the needs of my students." (Participant 2)

"Well, in a multigrade classroom, one of the biggest challenges is definitely the lack of appropriate instructional materials. It's hard to find resources that cater to the different grade levels I'm teaching simultaneously. Sometimes, the materials we do have are too advanced for the younger students or too basic for the older ones." (Participant 6)

Mismatch of Materials for Different Grade Levels. The difficulty of finding materials that suit the needs of all grade levels is compounded by the mismatch between materials and students' abilities. Teachers often face challenges when materials are either too simple for older students or too complex for younger ones, hindering effective learning for all.

"Handling instructional materials for multigrade classes is indeed challenging. One of the main problems is finding resources that are suitable for both Grade 1 and 2 students at the same time. Often, materials are either too advanced for the younger students or too basic for the older ones." (Participant 8)

"It can be difficult to keep everyone engaged and learning at their own pace when the materials don't quite fit. But I always try to see these challenges as opportunities to get creative." (Participant 6)

Q2. What ways did you adopt to address the challenges in instructional materials?

The responses from multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte reveal a variety of adaptive strategies they use to address the challenges posed by the lack of suitable instructional materials. These strategies highlight the teachers' creativity, resourcefulness, and commitment to providing engaging and effective learning experiences for students across different grade levels.

Involving Students in Creating Materials. One common strategy is involving students in the creation of learning materials. Teachers encourage students to design posters, charts, or other resources, making the learning experience more interactive and engaging for them while also easing the teacher's workload.

"I also involve my students in creating some of the materials. For example, they help design charts or posters that can be used across different grades. It's a great way to make learning more interactive." (Participant 1)

"I involve students in creating some of the materials and use versatile resources that can be adapted for different grades. This helps manage the workload and makes learning more engaging." (Participant 3)

Creating and Modifying Materials. Teachers also address the shortage of suitable materials by creating their own or modifying existing resources. This approach often involves combining materials from different sources to meet the needs of all grade levels, as well as adapting materials to ensure they are appropriate for the diverse academic levels within the classroom.

"I knew I had to be resourceful. I started creating my own materials, combining content from different sources to fit the needs of both grade levels. It's a lot of work, but it's worth it when I see the students engaging with the lessons." (Participant 5)

"To address these challenges, I've developed a few strategies. I modify existing materials to suit both grade levels, such as simplifying or expanding activities as needed. I also create my own resources that align with the learning goals for both Grade 3 and 4." (Participant 9)

Utilizing Technology and Multimedia. Another solution adopted by some teachers is the integration of technology, including educational apps and online resources. These tools are adaptable and can be customized for different grade levels, helping to bridge the gap in available resources. Additionally, multimedia resources and hands-on activities are used to make learning more interactive and relatable for students.

"I've started using technology more—apps and online resources that can be tailored for different levels. I also involve the students in making their own learning materials." (Participant 6)

"I've integrated multimedia and hands-on activities that can be scaled up or down to suit different needs. By keeping a flexible approach and being willing to innovate, I've managed to turn these challenges into opportunities for creative teaching." (Participant 8)

Collaboration with Other Teachers. Collaboration is another effective strategy. Teachers exchange ideas and share materials with their colleagues, which helps to supplement the limited resources available and provides new ideas for engaging and effective teaching.

"Collaborating with other teachers has also been very helpful; we share and exchange materials and ideas that work well in a multigrade setting." (Participant 10)

Classroom Management Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers

Table 6 presented the classroom management challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers.

Table 6. *Classroom Management Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers*

Statement	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I have hard time focusing on teaching my class and my classroom because of the urgent reports.	2.82	0.89	Agree	Moderately Evident
2. I have a hard time imposing punishments on my pupils who come to school late because of the distance from their homes to the school since most of them just walk.	2.37	0.90	Disagree	Less Evident
3. I have a hard time imposing punishments on my pupils who are often absent from our classes because they need to help their parents' work.	2.45	0.79	Disagree	Less Evident
4. I have a hard to managing well my pupils because I am sent to seminars/trainings.	2.44	0.82	Disagree	Less Evident
5. It is so hard to discipline my students because they are diversified and too many.	2.35	0.78	Disagree	Less Evident
Average	2.48	0.72	Disagree	Less Evident

Legend: 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree | 1.50 - 2.49 = Disagree | 2.50 - 3.49 = Agree | 3.50 - 4.00 = Strongly Agree
1.00 - 1.49 = Not Evident | 1.50 - 2.49 = Less Evident | 2.50 - 3.49 = Moderately Evident | 3.50 - 4.00 = Highly Evident

Table 6 indicates that teachers agree with moderate evidence that urgent reports disrupt their focus on teaching and classroom management, with a score of 2.82. However, they generally disagree (average of 2.48) with challenges related to imposing discipline, managing students during absences or training, and addressing diversity or class size. Overall, classroom management challenges are less evident.

In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion

Q1. Are multigrade classes difficult to manage? Why?

The responses from multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte reveal that managing multigrade classes is indeed a challenging task. Teachers often face difficulties balancing the varying needs of students from different grade levels. The following themes reflect the challenges they experience and the reasons behind them.

Differing Needs and Paces of Students. One of the main challenges in managing multigrade classes is the disparity in the needs and learning paces of students from different grades. Younger students require more attention and supervision, while older students tend to get impatient if not engaged effectively. Teachers must constantly adjust their focus to cater to both groups, which can be overw

elming.

"Yes, managing multigrade classes is definitely challenging, especially in grades 1 and 2. The younger kids need more attention, and the older ones often get bored if they have to wait too long." (Participant 1)

"Yes, managing multigrade classes can be quite challenging. The difficulty comes from having to address the diverse needs of different grade levels simultaneously." (Participant 7)

Balancing Multiple Lessons and Activities. Teachers also highlight the challenge of managing different lessons and activities simultaneously. Each grade level requires its own curriculum and set of learning objectives, and it can be difficult to keep everything organized and on track while also ensuring that students are engaged and learning.

"Imagine having two different grade levels in one room, each with their own lessons, activities, and needs. It's like trying to be in two places at once. One group might be working on math while the other is reading, and I have to make sure both are on track." (Participant 4)

"The challenge is not just in delivering the content but also in ensuring that each student gets the attention they need. It's a balancing act that requires constant adjustment and flexibility." (Participant 8)

Classroom Environment and Space Limitations. For some teachers, managing multigrade classes becomes even more difficult due to the physical limitations of their classrooms. Small spaces often mean that multiple students from different grade levels are learning in close quarters, making it harder to provide personalized attention or maintain focus across the group.

"Managing multigrade classes can be quite challenging, especially here in Siargao. Our classrooms are often small, with students of different ages and abilities all learning together." (Participant 6)

Emotional and Mental Exhaustion. The constant switching between different levels of instruction, managing diverse learning needs, and maintaining classroom order can lead to emotional and mental exhaustion. Teachers must be highly adaptable, constantly shifting their focus between different activities and levels of instruction.

"Managing students across various grades means constantly shifting my focus and keeping everyone on track. Each group has different needs, and it's exhausting to balance them all." (Participant 5)

"It's like trying to juggle two sets of expectations and keep all students engaged and progressing. The constant switching between different levels of instruction and maintaining focus can be demanding." (Participant 9)

Q2. How did you cope with difficulty in managing them?

The responses from the multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte highlight various coping strategies they use to manage the challenges of teaching multigrade ESL classes. These strategies emphasize organization, flexibility, and fostering a collaborative classroom environment. The following themes summarize their coping mechanisms:

Use of Visual Aids and Interactive Activities. Teachers frequently rely on visual aids and interactive activities to keep students engaged and focused. These tools help bridge the gap between different grade levels and make learning more accessible.

"I use a lot of visual aids and interactive activities to keep the students focused. Consistency is key, and involving the students in their own management helps a lot." (Participant 1)

"I use a lot of positive reinforcement and set up clear expectations for behavior. Regularly reviewing these expectations helps keep the classroom running smoothly." (Participant 1)

Encouraging Student Independence and Peer Support. Many teachers emphasize the importance of fostering student independence, particularly by giving students tasks they can complete on their own while the teacher focuses on other groups. Peer teaching, where older or more advanced students assist younger ones, also plays a significant role in easing the teacher's load and building a sense of teamwork.

"I learned to be very organized and planned my lessons carefully, making sure there's a good flow between the activities for both grades. I also taught the students to be more independent, giving them tasks they can do on their own while I focus on the other group." (Participant 4)

"I focus on staying organized with flexible lesson plans that can adapt to different needs. I use group work so older students can help younger ones, which also fosters teamwork." (Participant 6)

Patience, Adaptability, and Community Support. Teachers recognize the importance of patience and adaptability in managing a multigrade classroom. They also highlight the value of building a supportive classroom community, where students help each other, which not only makes the classroom more manageable but also fosters a positive learning environment.

"Patience and adaptability are the key. I build a strong classroom community where students help and support each other. I also rely

on group work and peer teaching." (Participant 5)

"I rely on the strengths of our community. Just like in our daily lives here in Siargao, we help each other. I've found that fostering a sense of teamwork among the students really helps." (Participant 7)

Staying Organized with Flexible Lesson Plans. Several teachers emphasize the importance of being organized and flexible in their lesson planning. They adapt their plans to meet the needs of different grade levels and adjust activities to keep all students engaged. This approach helps them handle the complexity of managing a multigrade classroom.

"I create detailed lesson plans that allow me to address the needs of both grade levels effectively. I use strategies like rotating between groups, where one group works independently while I provide targeted instruction to the other." (Participant 8)

"By staying organized and adaptable, I can handle the complexities of multigrade teaching and ensure that all students get the support they need." (Participant 9)

Language Barrier Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers

Table 7 presents the language barrier challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers.

Table 7. *Language Barrier Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers*

Statement	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. My pupils have different first dialects, that is why they struggle to communicate well in their group activities that require them to speak English.	2.44	0.92	Disagree	Less Evident
2. My first language is different from most of my pupils, so I struggle to talk to them whenever I translate English to their own dialects.	2.42	0.92	Disagree	Less Evident
3. My pupils have a poor English vocabulary stored in their minds, that is why it is hard on their part to understand the lessons that use English as a medium of instruction.	2.72	0.68	Agree	Moderately Evident
4. My learners are too shy to speak in English because they are not good at it.	2.74	0.70	Agree	Moderately Evident
5. My pupils get bored whenever I speak English when I discuss to them the lessons.	2.49	0.70	Disagree	Less Evident
Average	2.56	0.59	Agree	Moderately Evident

Legend: 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree / 1.50 - 2.49 = Disagree / 2.50 - 3.49 = Agree / 3.50 - 4.00 = Strongly Agree
1.00 - 1.49 = Not Evident / 1.50 - 2.49 = Less Evident / 2.50 - 3.49 = Moderately Evident / 3.50 - 4.00 = Highly Evident

The table above displays that teachers moderately agree (average of 2.56) that language barriers pose challenges in multigrade classrooms. Key issues include students' poor English vocabulary and their shyness to speak English, which hinders their understanding and participation. However, teachers generally disagree that differences in first dialects, translation struggles, or boredom during English discussions significantly impact learning. While language challenges are evident, they are not overwhelmingly problematic.

In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion

Q1. Can you consider local dialect as a barrier to learning English in MG classes? Why?

The responses from the multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte reveal a common concern regarding the impact of the local dialect on students' ability to learn English in a multigrade setting. While some teachers see the local dialect as a barrier, others believe it can also serve as a supportive tool in the learning process. The following themes summarize their views:

The Local Dialect as a Barrier to Learning English. Many teachers acknowledge that the local dialect, particularly Sinurigaonon, is a barrier because students are more comfortable using it than English. This language difference can slow down students' progress and create challenges in understanding and using English.

"Yes, definitely. The local dialect can be a barrier because many students are more comfortable with it than with English. This can slow down their progress and make it harder for them to understand and use English effectively." (Participant 1)

"Yes, Ma'am, I do consider the local dialect as a barrier to learning English, especially in multigrade classes. You see, the children here are more comfortable speaking our local dialect, Sinurigaonon. It's the language they use at home and with their friends, so when we switch to English in class, it can be a struggle for them." (Participant 6)

Local Dialect as a Steppingstone for Learning English. Some teachers do not see the local dialect as a barrier but rather as a helpful foundation. They believe that the students' proficiency in their native language can support their learning of English, especially if the dialect is used strategically to bridge the gap between languages.

"While the local dialect, like Sinurigaonon, can present some challenges in learning English, I don't see it as a barrier more like a steppingstone." (Participant 7)

"The local dialect can be a challenge, but I wouldn't necessarily call it a barrier. It's true that students are more comfortable with their native language, and this can make transitioning to English more difficult. However, the local dialect also provides a foundation that

can actually support English learning." (Participant 8)

Struggles with Transitioning to English. The transition from the local dialect to English is particularly challenging, as students are more accustomed to their native language. The shift to English can cause confusion and difficulty in grasping English concepts, affecting their overall learning experience.

"Yes, the local dialect can act as a barrier to learning English, especially in multigrade classrooms. Since students are accustomed to their native language, transitioning to English can be challenging. They might struggle with understanding and using English in a meaningful way because it's so different from what they're used to in their daily lives." (Participant 9)

"Yes, the local dialect can definitely be a barrier. Many students are more comfortable in their native language, which can make it difficult for them to learn English." (Participant 2)

Q2. How did you bridge the two languages in teaching English?

The responses from the multigrade teachers in Siargao Division, Surigao del Norte, reveal several strategies they use to bridge the gap between the local dialect and English in their classrooms. Teachers recognize the importance of making English lessons relatable and accessible by connecting them to students' experiences and native language. Below are the themes that summarize their approaches to bridging the two languages:

Code-Switching and Gradual Transition. Many teachers use code-switching as a strategy to help students transition from their local dialect to English. This method involves mixing English with the local dialect, which makes students feel more comfortable while gradually becoming familiar with English. Teachers introduce new concepts in the local dialect first and then transition to English, ensuring that students fully understand the lesson before using the second language.

"I knew I had to find a way to bridge the gap between Sinurigaonon and English. So, I started by using our local dialect as a steppingstone. I would explain difficult concepts in Sinurigaonon first to make sure they understood, and then gradually introduce the English terms." (Participant 4)

"I use a lot of code-switching, mixing Surigaonon and English to make things clearer. I also bring in local stories and examples to make English more relatable." (Participant 5)

Using Local Contexts and Cultural Examples. Teachers also incorporate local stories, experiences, and examples from the students' lives to make English lessons more relatable. By linking English vocabulary and phrases to things students are already familiar with, such as local traditions and events, they help students see the relevance of English in their everyday lives.

"I use contextual learning by linking English lessons to real-life situations that the students are familiar with. For example, I use local stories or experiences and explain how they relate to English vocabulary and phrases." (Participant 2)

"I start by explaining new ideas in Sinurigaonon so they fully understand the concept, then slowly transition to English. We do a lot of code-switching at first, using familiar words and phrases from the local dialect alongside English." (Participant 6)

Bilingual Materials and Visual Aids. Another common strategy is the use of bilingual materials and visual aids. Teachers create materials that include both the local dialect and English to reinforce understanding. Visual aids further help students connect the abstract nature of language with tangible, relatable objects and concepts, making learning more concrete.

"I create bilingual materials and use visual aids that can be understood regardless of the language. I also encourage students to use English in simple ways and provide support when they struggle with the language." (Participant 1)

"I bridge the two languages by using a combination of approaches. I start by introducing new English concepts alongside explanations in the local dialect, so students understand the material fully before transitioning to English." (Participant 7)

Positive Reinforcement and Encouragement. Teachers encourage students to use English, even if they make mistakes, by creating a supportive environment. Positive reinforcement is key in helping students feel confident when practicing English, and teachers use praise and motivation to encourage the use of English in various contexts.

"I create a positive reinforcement system where students receive praise for using English correctly. I also use language partners or buddies to provide additional practice and support." (Participant 3)

"I always told them, 'It's okay to mix English with Sinurigaonon as long as you're trying.' Over time, I saw their confidence grow, and they became more comfortable using English in class." (Participant 4)

Difference on Challenges of Multigrade ESL Teachers by Profile

The data presented in Table 8 examines the differences in the challenges faced by ESL multigrade teachers with respect to various profile variables.

Table 8. *Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Profile*

Profile	Variable	F	p	Decision on Ho	Inter'n
Age	Training	10.67	<0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Timetable	9.44	<0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Instructional Materials	2.22	0.11	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Classroom Management	4.43	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Language Barrier	1.45	0.24	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Gender	Training	1.23	0.27	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Timetable	0.00	0.95	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.13	0.72	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Classroom Management	1.67	0.20	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Language Barrier	0.11	0.74	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Civil Status	Training	3.50	0.06	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Timetable	7.44	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.00	1.00	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Classroom Management	5.96	0.02	Rejected	Significant
	Language Barrier	3.70	0.06	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Position	Training	4.73	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Timetable	2.89	0.06	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	4.88	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Classroom Management	2.40	0.10	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Language Barrier	1.42	0.25	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Grade Level Handled	Training	2.21	0.09	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Timetable	3.47	0.02	Rejected	Significant
	Instructional Materials	3.53	0.02	Rejected	Significant
	Classroom Management	1.78	0.16	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Language Barrier	2.27	0.08	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Length of Teaching Experience	Training	4.54	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Timetable	4.94	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Instructional Materials	1.05	0.37	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Classroom Management	2.45	0.07	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Language Barrier	2.21	0.09	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	Training	2.82	0.06	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Timetable	1.21	0.30	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.32	0.73	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Classroom Management	3.67	0.03	Rejected	Significant
	Language Barrier	0.23	0.80	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Performance	Training	4.16	0.02	Rejected	Significant
	Timetable	7.49	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Instructional Materials	16.98	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Classroom Management	7.68	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Language Barrier	10.89	0.00	Rejected	Significant
Mean Percentage Score Description	Training	1.11	0.30	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Timetable	0.37	0.54	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.05	0.82	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Classroom Management	0.44	0.51	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Language Barrier	0.10	0.75	Not Rejected	Not Significant

The findings indicate that multigrade teaching challenges are primarily influenced by age, length of teaching experience, civil status, grade level handled, position, and performance. These factors significantly impact areas such as training, timetable, classroom management, and instructional materials. Performance notably affects all areas, including language barriers, while gender, educational attainment, and mean percentage score show minimal to not significant. Overall, teachers' experience, roles, and performance play a critical role in shaping their challenges, while demographic factors like gender and education have little effect.

Table 9. *Scheffe's Test for Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Age*

Variable	Age		p	D	I
Training	21-29 (M=2.61)	30-39 (M=1.85)	.001	R	S
	21-29 (M=2.61)	40 and above (M=1.63)	.001	R	S
	30-39 (M=1.85)	40 and above	.637	NR	NS

Timetable	21-29 (M=3.12)	30-39 (M=2.64)	.002	R	S
	21-29 (M=3.12)	40 and above (M=2.47)	.001	R	S
	30-39 (M=2.64)	40 and above (M=2.47)	.584	NR	NS
Classroom Management	21-29 (M=2.77)	30-39 (M=2.35)	.027	R	S
	21-29 (M=2.77)	40 and above (M=2.32)	.077	NR	NS
	30-39 (M=2.35)	40 and above (M=2.32)	.987	NR	NS

Legend: D - Decision on Ho | I - Interpretation | R - Rejected | S - Significant | NR - Not Rejected | NS - Not Significant

Table 9 presented that younger multigrade teachers (21-29) face more challenges in training, timetable, and classroom management compared to multigrade teachers aged 30-39 and 40 and above. However, there are no significant differences between the 30-39 and 40 and above age groups in these areas.

Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Civil Status

The data presented in Table 10 examines the differences in the challenges faced by ESL multigrade teachers when grouped by civil status.

Table 10. Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Civil Status

Civil Status	Timetable	Classroom Management
Married	2.65	2.36
Single/Separated/Annulled/Widowed	3.00	2.71

Married ESL multigrade teachers face fewer challenges with timetable and classroom management compared to single, separated, annulled, or widowed multigrade teachers, who report more difficulties.

Table 11. Scheffe's Test for Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Position

Variable	Position	p	D	I
Training	Teacher I (M=2.25) Teacher II (M=1.6)	.137	NR	NS
	Teacher I (M=2.25) Teacher III & higher (M=1.66)	.037	R	S
	Teacher II (M=1.6) Teacher III & higher (M=1.66)	.988	NR	NS
Instructional Materials	Teacher I (M=2.61) Teacher II (M=2.29)	.347	NR	NS
	Teacher I (M=2.61) Teacher III & higher (M=2.15)	.015	R	S
	Teacher II (M=2.29) Teacher III & higher (M=2.15)	.862	NR	NS

Legend: D - Decision on Ho | I - Interpretation | R - Rejected | S - Significant | NR - Not Rejected | NS - Not Significant

The table above shows that Teacher I faces more challenges in training and instructional materials compared to Teacher II and Teacher III. The differences are significant when comparing Teacher I to Teacher III, but not between Teacher II and Teacher III.

Table 12. Scheffe's Test for Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Grade Level Handled

Variable	Grade Level Handled	p	D	I
Timetable	Grade 1 & 2 (M=3.12) Grade 3 & 4 (M=2.79)	.335	NR	NS
	Grade 1 & 2 (M=3.12) Grade 5 & 6 (M=2.54)	.020	R	S
	Grade 1 & 2 (M=3.12) Kindergarten and Other Grade Level (M=2.8)	.558	NR	NS
	Grade 3 & 4 (M=2.79) Grade 5 & 6 (M=2.54)	.433	NR	NS
	Grade 3 & 4 (M=2.79) Kindergarten and Other Grade Level (M=2.8)	1.000	NR	NS
	Grade 5 & 6 (M=2.54) Kindergarten and Other Grade Level (M=2.8)	.630	NR	NS
Instruct'l Materials	Grade 1 & 2 (M=2.77) Grade 3 & 4 (M=2.57)	.734	NR	NS
	Grade 1 & 2 (M=2.77) Grade 5 & 6 (M=2.21)	.030	R	S
	Grade 1 & 2 (M=2.77) Kindergarten and Other Grade Level (M=2.54)	.792	NR	NS
	Grade 3 & 4 (M=2.57) Grade 5 & 6 (M=2.21)	.154	NR	NS
	Grade 3 & 4 (M=2.57) Kindergarten and Other Grade Level (M=2.54)	1.000	NR	NS
	Grade 5 & 6 (M=2.21) Kindergarten and Other Grade Level (M=2.54)	.446	NR	NS

Legend: D - Decision on Ho | I - Interpretation | R - Rejected | S - Significant | NR - Not Rejected | NS - Not Significant

Teachers of Grades 1 & 2 faced more challenges with timetables and instructional materials compared to those teaching Grades 5 & 6. This shows that teachers' challenges vary depending on the grade level they handle. These findings highlight the need for support tailored to each grade level, particularly in managing time and accessing materials.

Table 13. Scheffe's Test for Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Length of Teaching Experience

Variable	Length of Teaching Experience	p	D	I
Training	1-5 years (M=2.32) 6-10 years (M=1.88)	.232	NR	NS
	1-5 years (M=2.32) 11-15 years (M=1.67)	.257	NR	NS

Timetable	1-5 years (M=2.32)	16-20 years (M=1.23)	.031	R	S
	6-10 years (M=1.88)	11-15 years (M=1.67)	.942	NR	NS
	6-10 years (M=1.88)	16-20 years (M=1.23)	.403	NR	NS
	11-15 years (M=1.67)	16-20 years (M=1.23)	.815	NR	NS
	1-5 years (M=2.92)	6-10 years (M=2.75)	.702	NR	NS
	1-5 years (M=2.92)	11-15 years (M=2.44)	.203	NR	NS
	1-5 years (M=2.92)	16-20 years (M=2.09)	.012	R	S
	6-10 years (M=2.75)	11-15 years (M=2.44)	.643	NR	NS
	6-10 years (M=2.75)	16-20 years (M=2.09)	.094	NR	NS
	11-15 years (M=2.44)	16-20 years (M=2.09)	.714	NR	NS

Legend: D - Decision on Ho | I - Interpretation | R - Rejected | S - Significant | NR - Not Rejected | NS - Not Significant

The table above shows that multigrade teachers with 1-5 years of experience face more challenges with training and timetables compared to those with 16-20 years of experience. There were no big differences between other experience groups.

Table 14. Scheffe's Test for Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Highest Educational Attainment		p	D	I
Classroom Management	Bachelor's Degree (M=2.47)	Master's Units (M=2.56)	.835	NR	NS
	Bachelor's Degree (M=2.47)	At Least Master's Degree (M=1.68)	.066	NR	NS
	Master's Units (M=2.56)	At Least Master's Degree (M=1.68)	.029	R	S

Legend: D - Decision on Ho | I - Interpretation | R - Rejected | S - Significant | NR - Not Rejected | NS - Not Significant

Based on Table 14, Teachers with Master's units face more classroom management challenges than those with a master's degree or higher. There were no significant differences between bachelor's degree holders and those with Master's units.

Table 15. Scheffe's Test for Difference on Challenges of ESL Multigrade Teachers when Grouped by Performance

Variable	Performance		p	D	I
Training	Satisfactory (M=2.71)	Very Satisfactory (M=1.97)	.023	R	S
	Satisfactory (M=2.71)	Outstanding (M=1.8)	.163	NR	NS
	Very Satisfactory (M=1.97)	Outstanding (M=1.8)	.919	NR	NS
Timetable	Satisfactory (M=3.34)	Very Satisfactory (M=2.69)	.002	R	S
	Satisfactory (M=3.34)	Outstanding (M=2.48)	.027	R	S
	Very Satisfactory (M=2.69)	Outstanding (M=2.48)	.749	NR	NS
Instruct'l Materials	Satisfactory (M=3.24)	Very Satisfactory (M=2.4)	.000	R	S
	Satisfactory (M=3.24)	Outstanding (M=1.8)	.000	R	S
	Very Satisfactory (M=2.4)	Outstanding (M=1.8)	.075	NR	NS
Classroom Management	Satisfactory (M=3.13)	Very Satisfactory (M=2.39)	.001	R	S
	Satisfactory (M=3.13)	Outstanding (M=2.2)	.034	R	S
	Very Satisfactory (M=2.39)	Outstanding (M=2.2)	.828	NR	NS
Language Barrier	Satisfactory (M=3.16)	Very Satisfactory (M=2.49)	.000	R	S
	Satisfactory (M=3.16)	Outstanding (M=2.12)	.002	R	S
	Very Satisfactory (M=2.49)	Outstanding (M=2.12)	.348	NR	NS

Legend: D - Decision on Ho | I - Interpretation | R - Rejected | S - Significant | NR - Not Rejected | NS - Not Significant

Teachers with a Satisfactory performance level faced more challenges in training, timetable, instructional materials, classroom management, and language barriers compared to those rated Very Satisfactory and Outstanding. There were no significant differences between Very Satisfactory and Outstanding teachers in these areas.

In this mixed-method study, integrated findings from both quantitative and qualitative phases reveal key insights into the challenges faced by multigrade ESL teachers. Quantitative data shows significant differences in performance across various areas: Training (p=0.023 between Satisfactory and Very Satisfactory), Timetable (p=0.002 between Satisfactory and Very Satisfactory, and p=0.027 between Satisfactory and Outstanding), Instructional Materials (p=0.000 between Satisfactory and Very Satisfactory, and p=0.000 between Satisfactory and Outstanding), Classroom Management (p=0.001 between Satisfactory and Very Satisfactory, and p=0.034 between Satisfactory and Outstanding), and Language Barrier (p=0.000 between Satisfactory and Very Satisfactory, and p=0.002 between Satisfactory and Outstanding).

Qualitative insights highlight teachers' resilience in overcoming challenges such as issues with training, timetable, lack of appropriate instructional materials, classroom management and overcoming language barriers, across multiple grade levels. Teachers adapt by modifying content, using creative strategies like code-switching, integrating lessons, involving students in material creation, and fostering teamwork. These findings underscore the importance of continuous professional development and the resourcefulness of teachers in navigating the complexities of multigrade classrooms.

Conclusions

This study concluded that multigrade ESL teachers in Siargao Division face significant challenges in time management and language concerns, with these issues being more prominent than those related to capability development through training and materials. Younger, less experienced, unmarried teachers in lower positions are particularly affected by difficulties in training, timetabling, and classroom management. Teachers of Grades 1 and 2 experience more challenges with timetables compared to those teaching Grades 5 and 6. Additionally, teachers with lower educational attainment struggle more with classroom management, and those with lower performance face challenges in all areas compared to their higher-performing counterparts. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to address the specific needs of these teachers. In response to these challenges, this study recommends the implementation of the "Enhanced Capacity for Multigrade ESL Teaching (ECMET)" program, which is designed to improve time management, language proficiency, and classroom management for multigrade ESL teachers. The ECMET program will focus on providing tailored support for younger, less experienced, and lower-performing teachers, particularly those with lower educational qualifications. Through targeted professional development and training opportunities, ECMET aims to enhance the performance of these teachers, equipping them with effective strategies for managing diverse classrooms and promoting a more inclusive learning environment. The implementation of ECMET will contribute to improving the overall quality of teaching and learning in Siargao Division's multigrade ESL classrooms, aligning with the study's objectives to address the challenges identified and provide actionable solutions for future practice.

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